

MiniLDV - Concept Study for a Small-Size Low-Cost Laser Doppler Velocimeter

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ABSTRACT

Main idea of this concept study MiniLDV is a small-size and low-cost Laser-Doppler Velocimeter. The sensor system will be based on laser diodes, photo diodes, and special multifunctional integrated optical circuits with embedded frequency shift functionality. Basis of MiniLDV will be a back scattering set-up with four beams, i.e. measurement possibility for two velocity components. The system is planned to be very small and with low weight. First simulations for size and energy density of the measuring volume are presented.

KEYWORDS: Laser-Doppler velocimetry, integrated optical circuit, simulation, measuring volume

INTRODUCTION

Laser-Doppler Velocimetry (LDV) goes back to the 70th of the last century when first ideas in this field came up ([1], [2]). The potential of this laser optical method without disturbance of the flow was quickly realized by many scientists and all over the world complex and expensive systems were built in research labs and at large wind tunnels ([3]).

For a longer time Ar-ion lasers were chosen as light sources. Normally photomultipliers (PM) were used as detectors for the weak scatter signals of small tracer particles. Signal processing in the beginning was done by counters, today it mainly has changed to FFT analysis. The necessary frequency shift of one of the two beams for detecting flow direction is done by use of a Bragg cell or by rotating grids.

The main principle set up of a forward scatter LDV system is given in Fig. 1. The details in Fig. 1 also show the structure of the measuring volume (fringes) and the corresponding detector signal (Doppler-burst). LDV systems offer a large variety of possible applications. But they also carry a main drawback: They are complex, heavy and very expensive.

Figure 1: Forward scatter LDV, principle set up (source: [4]).

CONCEPT

First ideas for Integrated Optical Circuits (IOC) came up in the last century in analogy to electrical integrated circuits ([5]). At the beginning passive wave guides were realized on glass substrate e.g. as beam splitters.

Main idea of our new system „MiniLDV” is a small-size and low-cost Laser-Doppler Velocimeter. The sensor system under development will consist of laser diodes (LD), photo diodes (PD), and special polymer-based multifunctional IOCs (MIOCs) with embedded frequency shift functionality, see Fig. 2.

Basis of MiniLDV will be a standard back scattering set-up with four beams (two different wave lengths, e.g. 784 nm and 850 nm), i.e. measurement possibility for two velocity components. The system is planned to be very small (length < 30 cm, diameter < 4 cm) and with low weight (mass < 2 kg).

Figure 2: Conceptual study MiniLDV, principle set up.

METHOD AND DISCUSSION

In a first step simulations for the LDV measuring volume were carried out using the standard equations from [2]. Starting with wavelength λ for different lens diameters D (=beam separation), focal lengths f , and laser powers P the following quantities were calculated for the measuring volume: fringe spacing (df), dimensions (diameter d_m , Volume V_m), and power density. Selected results are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulated results for MiniLDV measuring volume, line 3 is added for Ar-ion laser system

Input parameters	Fringe spacing	dimensions	Power density
850nm/D=20mm/f=40mm/P=50mW	0.95 μ m	$d_m=43\mu\text{m}/V_m=81,134\mu\text{m}^3$	0.616 $\mu\text{W}/\mu\text{m}^3$
850nm/D=40mm/f=80mm/P=50mW	0.95 μ m	$d_m=86\mu\text{m}/V_m=649,076\mu\text{m}^3$	0.077 $\mu\text{W}/\mu\text{m}^3$
514nm/D=50mm/f=250mm/P=300mW	1.31 μ m	$V_m=6,355,376\mu\text{m}^3$	0.047 $\mu\text{W}/\mu\text{m}^3$

Comparing a MiniLDV set up (line 2 in Tab. 1) with a standard Ar-ion laser system (line 3) it can be seen that the power densities in the measuring volumes are close together. This result indicates that the needs for MiniLDV detector sensitivity are in the same order as yet.

CONCLUSIONS

In principle, small-size low-cost LDV is possible! At the moment polymer-based MIOCs can be designed and produced in the near IR range. But LDV manufacturers report that LDV users prefer systems in the visible range. This dilemma will be solved in the nearer future by MIOC designers, hopefully. At this time a variety of new applications for LDV will come up, such as small wind tunnels, water channels, climate chambers, tube flows, and meteorological wind measurements (including an estimate of fine dust concentration in the air).

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